

SmartCorners

D7.2

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan (2)

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ELAPHE	Elaphe Propulsion Technologies
HER	HERONsports B.V.
BLW	Bluways International BVBA
AIG	Armengaud Innovate GmbH
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
TUIL	Technische Universität Ilmenau
UEMI	Urban Electric Mobility Initiative GmbH
AVL	AVL List GmbH

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1 Executive Summary

As electric vehicles (EVs) gain traction, optimising their design and operation becomes crucial. Smart corner systems (SCS) offer a promising solution, integrating in-wheel motor (IWM)-based propulsion, brake, steering and suspension systems. Realising the full potential of IWMs leaves room for sophisticated control strategies to manage diverse vehicle functionalities. In this context, the EU-funded SmartCorners project will use artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning to revolutionise EVs by enhancing design, energy management, user comfort, and recycling processes. Specifically, the project will focus on skateboard-like chassis configurations and predictive vehicle-level thermal management. Accelerated by advanced simulation and validation, the project will reduce development time and cost, support Europe's competitive position in the automotive industry and positively influence end user acceptance of future EVs [1].

The aim of this deliverable D7.2 is to provide an update to the already submitted and approved deliverable D7.1, that outlined the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plans for the first period, by providing the methodology for communication, dissemination and exploitation until the end of the project.

2 Introduction

Deliverable D7.1, submitted by M7 of the project duration, has laid the grounds for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities pursued in the SmartCorners project. The deliverable presented the methodology laid out specifically for the SmartCorners project and this methodology has been followed and further enhanced as the project continued over the last period.

Deliverable D7.2 will lay out the plan on communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies planned for the next period in the SmartCorners project.

The following figure shows how the project's Key Exploitable Results (KER) (for readability reduced to 9 KER, while the process is adopted to all 13 KER of the project as listed in Table 1) will increase their outreach and impact through specific communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies that are planned and performed.

Figure 1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation for Outreach and Impact

The table below lists all project outputs of the SmartCorners project. For a better understanding the project outcomes are grouped into five different assets according to the grant agreement.

Project output = KER	Actions
Asset 1 "Wheel Corner Design"	
PO – 01 Wheel Corner with IWM and integrated chassis actuators.	Simulation, design, preliminary validation, unit testing.
PO – 02 Novel integrated powertrain and chassis controller.	Controller customisation and testing for the specific SCS topology.

PO – 03 SW with adaptable RT AI module for wheel positioning control.	Simulation, Control SW development, Unit testing, Bench testing.
Asset 2 “User-centred Thermal and Cabin Comfort Management”	
PO – 04 AI preconditioning of the thermal system control.	AVL will set up a learning algorithm that detects if a user is about to use the car. AVL DE will use the information to precondition the TS.
PO – 05 Adaptive use of recirculation flap	It will be adapted to the ambient conditions and the number of passengers to demisting and save heating power at the same time.
PO – 06 AI adaption of the comfort settings to user preferences.	Simulation of an adaption and calibration towards a specific user preference.
Asset 3 “Global EV Motion Control”	
PO – 07 Slip control with dynamic tuning and vehicle speed estimator.	Development of AI speed estimator based on ELAPHE vehicle data. Interface for vehicle and environment context-driven dynamic adjustment of control parameters
PO – 08 Pitch, roll and yaw control as a part of a simultaneous 6 DoF control.	Determining comfort behaviour objectives. Development of a vehicle pitch, roll and yaw controllers with IWMs. Model-in-the-loop (MiL), HiL & vehicle validation including validated physics model.
PO – 09 Secondary mode damping control as a part of simultaneous 6DoF control.	Development of secondary damping control with external input interface for road profile (e.g., camera or cloud data). Test with MiL, HiL and on vehicle.
Asset 4 “Smart EV Optimal Operation Management”	
PO – 10 Virtual sensors, including road grip, wheel acceleration and suspension travel.	Modelling virtual sensors with AI approaches. Gathering data with existing vehicle for the training of virtual sensors. Virtual sensing validation via MiL, HiL and on the vehicle.
PO – 11 AI path planning.	Concept development, model building, power management control.
Asset 5 “DT Methodology of User-centred EV design”	
PO – 12 Digital twinning of EV with independent corners.	Implementation, validation and use for design and control.
PO – 13 DTs for AI training.	Build up digital twin model for AI training. AVL DE will do the modelling and AVL will set up the development environment.

Table 1: Main project outputs and relevant type of innovation actions [2]

3 Communication

This section will give a closer look on the communication strategies and channels that are and have been used in the project.

During the first period of the project, basic communication material and communication channels have been established; this included the setup of the project website, the LinkedIn channel and the SmartCorners Zenodo community. Furthermore, SmartCorners is actively contributing to the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities under the umbrella of the E-VOLVE cluster¹. These activities will further be continued, elaborated and extended.

During the first period of the project, compared to the initial deliverable D7.1, further communication channels have been established. These will be presented in the following sections and strategically addressed in the upcoming period.

3.1 2Zero Project Outcomes

The co-programmed partnership towards zero emission road transport (2Zero) has set up a further element to support the project’s communication; a dedicated area on the 2Zero website for project outcomes.

Figure 2: 2Zero project outcomes²

SmartCorners plans to actively cooperate with 2Zero in increasing the outreach of the publications / public deliverables.

¹ www.evolvecluster.eu

² <https://www.2zeroemission.eu/projects/project-outcomes/>

3.2 RhoDAS multi-stakeholders platform

Figure 3: RhoDAS multi-stakeholders platform³

The project RhoDAS⁴ is an E-VOLVE cluster partner project collaborating with SmartCorners and has set up a multi-stakeholders platform as a „collaborative space to access resources and gain insights into the state-of-the-art research and development currently being conducted in the electric mobility sector“ [3]. Results presented are organized in the sections:

- Technology & Components
- Circular Economy
- Resources
- E-VOLVE Cluster

We are looking forward to contributing to this platform with the results generated in the SmartCorners project.

3.3 SmartCorners Website

The SmartCorners website, established in the beginning of the project and described in deliverable D7.1, has been further extended by

- a) continuous updating of the news section and
- b) by introducing the section „results for impact“.

Within the website’s results section, the public available results of the SmartCorners project are presented at a central place. The website is structured into the following categories:

- Material (leaflets, roll-up, logo, etc.)
- Deliverables (all public deliverables)

³ <https://stakeholders.rhodas.eu>

⁴ <https://www.rhodas.eu>

- Publications
- Videos (project video, records of webinars, etc.)
- And even more (newsletters, presentations, etc.)

Figure 4: SmartCorners Website - results for impact⁵

This section will be a central area to disseminate project results, being displayed for the SmartCorners audience.

3.4 Events

Participating to events is a central element in project communication / dissemination. There already have been many events and conferences the SmartCorners partners were attending, and they are even intensifying the event participation in the coming months. Examples are highlighted in the following subsections:

3.4.1 European Researchers' Night

The European Researchers' Night "Life is Science"⁶ is taking place on September 26, 2025, and in the case of Austria, in Graz. The theme of the 2025 edition is "in a world turned upside down" and the event communication includes:

- Presentation at the event website
- The stand itself

⁵ <https://smartcorners.eu/results/>

⁶ <https://www.lifeisscience.at>

- Interviews for podcasts

Figure 5: European Researchers Night - Life is Science

SmartCorners will be present with a stand by AIG and AVL DiTEST, covering the SmartCorners demonstrator, that has been created between AVL DiTEST and FH Joanneum as part of a student's engineering project. Kids and their parents visiting the stand will have the chance to explore the "smart corners" of vehicles and how the in-wheel motor technology is affecting vehicle development and driving behaviour. It is designed to attract age levels from 6 to 18 as well as their parents.

In 2024, the project EM-TECH participated to this event, that attracted more than 1000 visitors [4]. It was a great success, and we are looking forward to presenting SmartCorners during this year's edition of the event.

3.4.2 Towards the sustainable vehicle era (ToSVE) 2025 / 2026

Towards the sustainable vehicle era (ToSVE)⁷, organized by the interdepartmental Center for Automotive Research and Sustainable mobility (CARS) and Power Electronics Innovation Center (PEIC) inside POLITO, offers a yearly platform to present project achievements in form of

- a) Poster Session,
- b) Prototype Exhibition, and
- c) Lab Visits.

3.4.3 IAA Transportation Hannover 2026

The International Motor Show Germany with focus on commercial transportation, which is known in Germany as "Internationale Automobil-Austellung" (IAA) Transportation was hold

⁷ <https://tsve.polito.it/conference/>

3.6 In-Wheel Motor Day - Press Conference

The project consortium is organizing a press conference in conjunction with a hands-on demonstration event hosted by ELAPHE at a proving ground in Slovenia on July 2025. This event will offer journalists, technical experts, and project partners an exclusive opportunity to experience first-hand driving multiple technology demonstrator vehicles powered by ELAPHE's advanced IWM systems.

During the press conference, the SmartCorners project will be presented alongside the EM-TECH and HighScape Horizon Europe projects. The demonstration will showcase ELAPHE's direct-drive IWM technology, highlighting key benefits such as independent torque control, improved vehicle packaging, ultra-fast response, software-defined vehicle character, and proprietary vibroacoustic tuning for enhanced driving experience.

The press conference and demonstration aim to demonstrate the real-world applications of EU-funded research innovations, specifically focusing on how software-defined vehicle motion control at the wheel level significantly enhances vehicle performance, comfort, and stability. The event will also dispel common misconceptions about unsprung mass and system complexity, providing tangible evidence of the advancements in sustainable and efficient EV technologies.

This demonstration event is expected to significantly increase media visibility and stakeholder engagement for the SmartCorners project, fostering further dissemination and exploitation opportunities for the project outcomes.

The corresponding press release is available on our website⁹.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15772163>

4 Dissemination

4.1 Project Documentation

As established in deliverable D7.1 the deliverables that have a public nature will be uploaded to the Zenodo platform and, as mentioned in section 3.3, can also be found on the project website.

The following deliverables from the SmartCorners project will be available publicly (sorted by due date):

No.	Deliverable Content
D1.1¹⁰	Report on SmartCorners technologies and user-centric vehicle control functions: overview of the smart corner technologies, incl. specifications and control system functions
D7.1¹¹	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan
D3.1	Design report on thermal and cabin comfort control: analysis of thermal system design and thermal system controller concepts. Decision based on cost, performance and complexity for the most promising concepts.
D7.2	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan, detailing the CDE plans towards project end
D7.3	Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Report, documenting actions and results achieved by the engagement and promotion strategies (V1)
D5.1	Innovative predictive control solutions supported by fleet data: chassis controllers based on NMPC and NNMPC strategies, vertical tire force-vectoring control and wheel kinematic control algorithms, supported by off-board data, cloud computing and AI-based solutions (V1)
D1.4	Report on validated simulation models: simulation results for SmartCorners solutions
D2.3	Smart-e-corner components susp. arms and upright, ride quality control actuator, x-by-wire chassis control actuator, power electronics for suspension actuation systems)
D3.3	Report on final thermal and cabin comfort control; Document the final results of the controller's performance. Describe the limitations and how they can be addressed in future projects.
D4.4	Digital twin model of the EV with SmartCorners topology benchmark: A benchmark of the accuracy of the digital representation of the EV with SmartCorners topology on component and system levels, enabling performance analysis and optimisation of hardware and software.

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15607462>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15607552>

D4.5	XIL Validation environment workflow: An agile model-based XIL validation workflow that improves execution time, reliability, repeatability, and cost-effectiveness for various stages of development and testing.
D5.4	Innovative predictive control solutions supported by fleet data: chassis controllers based on NMPC and NNMPC strategies, vertical tire force-vectoring control and wheel kinematic control algorithms, supported by off-board data, cloud computing and AI-based solutions (V2)
D6.3	Replication report: Report on replicability of smart corner concepts towards multiple vehicle segments
D7.4	Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Report, documenting actions and results achieved by the engagement and promotion strategies (V2)

Table 2: List of public deliverables [6]

At the time of writing of this deliverable, the deliverables D1.1 and D7.1 are submitted and approved, thus publicly available on Zenodo and linked to the project website. Deliverable D3.1 is submitted but not yet approved and will be published as soon as this is performed. The same procedure is to be applied to the upcoming deliverables as soon as they are approved.

4.2 KER one pager

In order to support the outreach of each individual KER, the project partners will develop “OnePagers” summarizing the main impact and benefits of each KER for communication and path towards exploitation purpose. As mentioned in section 3.5 a social media campaign will lead to the publication of the one pagers. The following figure shows the planned design with focus on the KER name and description, the main impact of the result, the benefits and contact.

Figure 7: KER one pager template

4.3 Presentation at Conferences

SmartCorners will be presented at several conferences in the next months of the project. At the time of writing this deliverable, we can present the following highlights, assuming papers will be accepted for TRA 2026 and SAE WCX 2026:

4.3.1 Conference on Results from Road Transport Research – RTR 2026

With the 2Zero projects being invited to present at the Conference on Results from Road Transport Research – short RTR – the 2026 edition will be the place for SmartCorners to present the results achieved so far. In 2025, the conference attracted a summary of 900 participants, with 500 participating in place and 400 online.

4.3.2 Transport Research Arena – TRA 2026

The Transport Research Arena is a bi-annual conference for the transport sector. The 2024 edition attracted more than 4000 participants and 150 exhibitors [7]. At the time of writing this deliverable, the due date of the abstract submission for TRA2026 is approaching. The SmartCorners project partners have submitted a corresponding abstract with the decision on acceptance is still pending.

4.3.3 SAE WCX 2026

SmartCorners has already been presented at SAE WCX 2025; with a common paper together with the projects MINDED¹² and EFFEREST¹³. Looking forward to the SAE WCX 2026, the SmartCorners project plans to be present again and is currently working on the submission to be finalized until the beginning of September 2025.

4.4 Advocate Ecosystem Platforms

With the project results being increasingly available, it is the right time to strengthen the exchange with the advocate ecosystem platforms. The following table shows which associations are available through consortium partners.

BDVA	AVL, AIG
EPOSS	AIG, AVL, ELA,
AIOTI	AIG
ERTRAC	AVL
EARPA	AVL, POLITO

Table 3: Association / Partner Mapping

The SmartCorners project will use these connections with the platform to push the dissemination activities through broader channels.

¹² <https://www.minded-project.eu>

¹³ <https://efferest-project.eu>

5 Exploitation

The linkage of project expectations, project partners involved, and potential business activities through products, services, and/or knowledge gained from the project is a vital aspect for reaching the expected benefits / impacts.

5.1 Roadmap for Exploitation

In the first period of the project, the SmartCorners project consortium decided to consult services from the Horizon Results Booster¹⁴ (now Horizon Booster), choosing the “Go to Market support methodology”. As part of this service, an exploitation roadmap for KER 1 has been developed, a methodology to be continued for the further KER developed by the project.

Recommendations have been given including formulating unique value propositions, developing value proposition canvas (VPC) and business model canvas (BMC) as well as uploading KERs to the Horizon Results Platform¹⁵, which will be pursued in the upcoming period of the project.

5.2 Value Proposition Canvas / Business Model Canvas

Following the recommendations by the Horizon Results Booster consultation, the project consortium will develop VPCs and BMCs as a basis for the future exploitation of the KER. Corresponding templates have been developed as can be seen in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Figure 8: Value Proposition Canvas template

¹⁴ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu>

¹⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

Figure 9: Business Model Canvas template

6 Conclusion

The present deliverable outlines the plans of the consortium to work on communication, dissemination and especially exploitation towards the project end. Methodologies and pathways have been outlined relying on the expertise from the Horizon Results Booster consultation, as well. The project consortium will continue working on developing appropriate plans for each of the KER and partner individual activities.

A clear highlight will be the representation of major events thus reaching out to various stakeholders:

- SAE WCX 2026
- RTR 2026
- TRA 2026
- IAA Transportation 2026

The timing of these activities taking place in the final project year, allows building a strong momentum to support the exploitation plans developed for the KERS.

7 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long text
2Zero	Towards zero emission road transport
AI	Artificial intelligence
AIOTI	The Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
EARPA	European Automotive Research Partners Association
EPOSS	European Platform on Smart Systems Integration
ERTRAC	European Road Transport Research Advisory Council
EV	Electric Vehicle
FH	Fachhochschule
HiL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
IAA	Internationale Automobil-Ausstellung
IWM	In-Wheel Motor
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MiL	Model-in-the-Loop
NMPC	Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
NNMPC	Neural Network Model Predictive Control
PO	Project Output
RTR	Road Transport Research
ToSVE	Toward the Sustainable Vehicle Era
TRA	Transport Research Arena
RT	Real-Time
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SCS	Smart Corner Systems
TS	Thermal System
VPC	Value Proposition Canvas
WCX	World Congress Experience
WP	Work Package

XIL	Anything-in-the-loop
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8 Sources

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